

Annex 2. Bid form for a mentoring round

Version 1.2 of 20 March 2025

SECTION A: ORGANISATIONAL DETAILS

Provide details of the organisation submitting the BRIDGE mentoring round bid in the fields below

- A1. Name organisation:** Datahub, Institute of Tropical Medicine (ITM)
- A2. Contact person name:** Tine Verdonck
- A3. Contact person email:** tverdonck@itg.be
- A3. Address:** Nationalestraat 155, 2000, Antwerp, Belgium
- A4. Website:** Institute: <https://www.itg.be/en>
Datahub: <https://www.itg.be/en/research/datahub>

A5. Research profile

Use the text box below to describe the organisation's main research areas and activities, which may include an overview of thematic and/or geographical areas. Feel free to include external links for more detailed information.

ITM's historical niche is in tropical medicine and international health. Research activities range from basic to operational research and are organised in three scientific departments, which focus on pathogens (biomedical sciences), patients (clinical sciences), and populations (public health). ITM is specialised in health problems affecting people who live in low-resource settings or are marginalised in other ways. An overview of the main research themes at ITM is available [here](#).

A6. Training profile

Use the text box below to describe the organisation's main training areas and activities, including undergraduate, postgraduate and short courses. Feel free to include external links for more information.

ITM offers different types of postgraduate training: postgraduate certificates, short courses, master programmes and PhD training. There are three master (MSc) programmes: in Public Health, in Tropical Medicine and in Global One Health. ITM staff also co-supervise more than 100 PhD students. An overview of ITM's educational offer is available [here](#).

SECTION B: OVERVIEW OF THE PROPOSED MENTORING ROUND

Provide characteristics of the proposed round of mentoring in the fields below.

B1. Number of BRIDGE mentoring rounds: 1

B2. Duration of one round: one year

B3. Number of mentees: 8 to 10

B4. Number of mentors: 8 to 10

B5. Format:

Open: we plan to launch an open call and recruit participants among those who apply spontaneously.

Closed: we will not launch an open call but select participants from a specific organisation or network.

Semi-open: we will launch an open call but reserve a few positions for people from a specific organisation.

Comment: We would like to enrol two mentees and two mentors from our staff at ITM. The remaining positions will be filled after an open call which will be communicated in ITM's network of alumni and collaborators.

SECTION C: PROPOSED TIMELINE

Specify in the text boxes below the proposed start date (month and year) for each phase of the programme. Suggested durations are provided as an indication based on a one year overall duration, but are not prescribed. Overlap between activities is possible.

C1. Recruitment and selection of mentors and mentees (suggested duration: 1 month)

Start date: April 2025

End date: May 2025

Total duration (in months): 1 month

C2. Preparatory training for mentors and mentees (suggested duration: 1 month)

Start date: May 2025

End date: June 2025

Total duration (in months): 1 month

C3. Project-based mentoring: application of BRIDGE guidelines (suggested duration: 10 months)

Start date: June 2025

End date: May 2026

Total duration (in months): 10 months

C4. Development of intervision groups (suggested duration: 1 year)

Start date: June 2025

End date: June 2026

Total duration (in months): 12 months

C5. Assessment and certification (suggested duration: 2 weeks)

Start date: June 2026

End date: June 2026

Total duration (in months): 0.5 months

C6. Monitoring (suggested duration: start at recruitment, up to one year after certification)

Start date: April 2025

End date: June 2027

Total duration (in months): 26 months

C7. Closure (suggested duration: 1 month)

Start date: May 2026

End date: June 2026

Total duration (in months): 1 month

SECTION D: PROPOSED RESOURCES

Specify in the text boxes below the level of effort, material input and organisational resources that the applicant can provide to facilitate hosting of the proposed BRIDGE mentoring round.

D1. Level of effort (staff time in full time equivalent and working days per week)

- Coordinator (Tine Verdonck): 0.05 full time equivalent (1/4 working day per week)
- Pedagogical adviser (Lai Jiang): 0.05 full time equivalent (1/4 working day per week)
- Administrative support: 0.05 full time equivalent (1/4 working day per week)

Comment: this is the estimated average time over the course of one year. In reality, we estimate that the time investment will fluctuate, with higher time investments in the first and last months of the mentoring round.

D2. Material input (tangible resources other than staff time that can support programme implementation such as Moodle environment, server space, etc.)

Free use of ITM's Moodle learning environment for developing teaching materials, hosting one round, and storing all data linked to that round. Participants of the mentoring round (mentors and mentees) can access the learning environment up to three years after the start date of the round. Representatives of the BRIDGE steering committee can always access that data (no end date).

D3. Organisational input (financial and/or logistic capacity to host meetings)

Organisation of three workshops in Antwerp with representatives of the BRIDGE steering committee: two before the start (to brainstorm about the set up) and one after the end of the mentoring round (to evaluate and hand over the materials).

Contact with ITM's staff and our network of alumni and epidemiologists (including colleagues working in partner institutes) for the recruitment of mentors and mentees.

D4. Other resources (any other relevant input)

Expertise in BRIDGE guidelines (co-authoring the original guidelines, participating in pilot mentoring initiative), global health epidemiology (research, teaching), organising courses and selecting candidates for master and PhD training.

Promotion of the BRIDGE mentoring programme via the ITM datahub website.